

STRUCTURAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL MODEL OF THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING REFLEXIVE POSITIVITY IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Аннотация

В данной статье раскрывается структурно-организационная модель процесса развития рефлексивной позитивности у будущих учителей. Также анализируются основные блоки модели, этапы реализации модели и совокупность организационных и педагогико-психологических условий.

Ключевые слова: развитие рефлексивной позитивности, будущие учителя, структурно-организационная модель, студент, компонент, моделирование, принцип, блок.

Annotation

This article reveals the structural and organizational model of the process of developing reflexive positivity in future teachers. The main blocks of the model, the stages of the model implementation and the set of organizational and pedagogical-psychological conditions are also analyzed.

Keywords: development of reflexive positivity, future teachers, structural and organizational model, student, component, modeling, principle, block.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda refleksiv pozitsiyani rivojlantirish jarayonining strukturaviy-tashkiliy modeli ochib berilgan. Shuningdek, modelning asosiy bloklari, modelni amalga oshirish bosqichlari hamda tashkiliy va pedagogik-psixologik sharoitlar majmui tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: refleksiv pozitsiyani rivojlantirish, bo'lajak o'qituvchilar, strukturaviy-tashkiliy model, talaba, komponent, modellashtirish, tamoyil, blok.

In the following years, large-scale work is being carried out in our country to create a higher education system in accordance with the priorities of socio-economic development and the requirements of international standards.

At the same time, a number of problems remain, which become an obstacle to improving the quality of education in higher education institutions, carrying out comprehensive reforms in the Republic, and ensuring the active participation of these educational institutions in social and economic updates [1].

Modern research is envisaged in various ways, within which the modeling of problems is central, which, as a rule, is complemented by design methods and allows you to identify objects of pedagogical reality. The modeling method, which provides for the development of a block structure of an integrated research process, is very relevant today and allows us to improve scientific knowledge and expand the boundaries of pedagogical science.

The researcher's choice of a specific form or type of existing models depends on the amount of scientific knowledge and the scope of their application.

Also, the type of models can be classified according to the developed criteria and parameters. The theory, specific tasks and justification for the implementation of the study can be modeled by a future teacher in the process of developing reflexive positivity. University students should develop an effective assessment of activities, a consistent reflection of the path to achieving the intended goal in their activities, the future teacher should learn self-analysis, self-observation (Fig. 1).

Based on the classification of the theoretical knowledge obtained, we have identified the main blocks of the model, which are: organizational and managerial, guiding-target, content-technological, criteria-predictive and final-sequential blocks. 1.

Organizational and managerial block - the purpose of this block is to analyze, generalize, and draw conclusions from the problem of developing reflexive positivity in a future teacher. In the theory and practice of management of educational systems, in particular, in the management of the development of reflexive positivity, first of all, the basic principles are highlighted [2; 120]:

The principle of humanization and democratization of educational system management provides for the development of the initiative of the university administration, teachers and the entire student community.

Transparency, openness, the ability to maximize the use of information, the fact that every teacher is involved in the affairs and problems of the university as a whole, that the staff does not care about them.

Giving priority to the student's personality means making a decision about humane values. The principle of humanism in education management expresses, first of all, orientation towards the individual, recognition of human dignity and expression of trust in him.

Scheme-1. A model of the process of developing a reflexive position in a future teacher

Consistency and integrity in management (as a whole) is a methodology of a systematic approach to education management that encourages the administration of a university and gives a clear idea of its key features as a system. The category "system" provides for the possibility of separating one whole, elements or components of the structure.

This principle also provides for effective interaction of all managerial functions in the activities of the university administration and the teaching staff. In management, consistency and unity indicate that management activities are logical, consistent, and mutually beneficial.

The principle of collegiality and unity of command in management is aimed at eliminating authoritarianism in the management of the pedagogical process of the university. In management, the most important thing is to rely on the knowledge and experience of colleagues, develop and discuss collective solutions, compare different points of view on a particular problem, organize discussions and make the necessary and correct decisions.

Nevertheless, collegiality does not negate the responsibility of each person in the community for the decisions made.

The principle of completeness and objectivity of information in management presupposes the availability of reliable and complete information in the work. Data completeness is reliability and accuracy in the selection, analysis and processing of data. Managing the development of reflexive positivity in a future teacher is a rather complex process, which implies the need to take into account all aspects of management, such as teachers, students and administration [3; 256].

2. The directional-target block of the improved model on our part provides for the following constructive elements: a) the student's awareness of the essence and content of the concept of "reflexive positivity"; b) that the future teacher is focused on developing reflexive positivity in himself and has such an instruction; c) the result is an advanced reflexive pose.

The student must understand the importance and necessity of reflexive positivity as a professionally significant quality, which subsequently contributes to the effective implementation of the reflexive process, the development and self-development of the future teacher, affects the creative approach to his activities and high results.

The development of components of reflexive personality positivity is aimed at ensuring the fulfillment of the following necessary professionally significant functions, namely: conscious regulation, planning and control of thinking; objective assessment of one's own personality and one's own thoughts, and as a result – efficiency and professionalism in solving professional issues.

The main directions of the development of reflexive positivity among students are: a) a social order for a specialist with a developed reflexive position of society; b) the student's personal interest and the need for reflexive activity [4; 624].

The designation of a goal by a future teacher is an idea of future professional activity, which allows the student to focus all his energy on developing a reflective pose. The student's ability to set a goal for himself is to understand desires and needs, awareness of expected results and achievements.

The set goals also serve as a criterion for evaluating the expenditure of personal enthusiasm, time and funds that contribute to the development of reflexive positivity in a future teacher. The result of the development of reflexive positivity in a student is a high level of development of need–motivational, communicative-relational, emotional-functional, sense-organizing, cognitive-analytical and professionally traceable components.

3. The content and technological block of the presented model contains, aimed at forming a reflexive position of technology and elective courses. Among them, we attributed the experience of A.A. Derkach and V.G. Zazikin on reflexive learning, suggesting that students should: be able to identify and analyze their mistakes, understand the moral norms and spiritual values of society, realize the importance of a reflexive position that helps to think critically, think independently, plan their activities, and be critical of society.

Technologies such as the essay "Man as a value" and the group reflection "Modern educational psychologist" should help in this.

The student is often unsure of himself, has doubts about his future professional responsibility, in this regard, we have included such technology as writing a professional biography – "Gratitude to myself", "Me and my past".

The Ladder technology allows future teachers to build their own professional ladder by choosing one or another "step". More significant concepts are located on the lower "rungs of the ladder", which are a kind of foundation, building on less significant ones.

The content component of this block includes such means of educating and training a teacher as his pedagogical skills, mastery of oratory, intonation, voice, pedagogical intuition, teaching aids and the material and technical base of the university. In the logic of the presentation of our research, in accordance with the set goal, objectives, and research problem, the elective course developed by us, as well as the system of its technological support, acts as the main technology for the formation of a reflective position among future teachers.

4. The criterion-assessment block involves the development of criteria, indicators and levels of formation of a reflective position among future teachers; diagnostic techniques and methods of mathematical statistics for processing research results. We consider the criteria of the reflexive position of the future teacher from several sides. First, criteria are necessary to measure evaluation and judgment.

A criterion is a critical value responsible for the presence or absence of a certain ability or personality quality of a teacher responsible for the formation of a reflective position, as well as attitudes, motives and trends in the development of this quality. Secondly, the criteria act as an indicator that will allow us to assess the growth of a reflective position, and the impact of this quality on improving the general professional training of a future teacher.

And thirdly, the criteria act as socially approved norms and algorithms for the implementation of a teacher's professional activity. The final block of the structural and organizational model of the process of formation of reflexive positivity in a future teacher is a set of pedagogical and psychological conditions that form the organizational and substantive basis of the model.

Thus, the model of the process of forming a reflexive position for a future teacher includes: the purpose, principles, and the following blocks: employers' requirements for the level of teacher training; state requirements for the professional training of teachers (the activity of a teacher includes a number of functions:

developmental, diagnostic, therapeutic, correctional, advisory, control and evaluation, analytical, etc.);

organizational and management block (principles that are taken into account when implementing the model);

orientation-target block (the process of students' awareness of the content and essence of a reflective position;

students' attitude to the formation of a reflective position; as a result, a formed reflective position);

content-technological (elective courses and technologies);

criteria-evaluative (criteria, indicators and levels of formation of a reflective position);

final-effective (the result of a higher the level of formation of a reflexive position).

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